

SYNDROME MELLORY-WEISS

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Mallory-Weiss tears are non-penetrating tears in the distal esophagus and proximal stomach, which can be caused by frequent vomiting and hiccups. They cause bloody vomiting, which in turn is the main symptom of Mallory-Weiss syndrome. Currently, this syndrome is quite common and accounts for 4 to 11% of gastric bleeding in the upper gastrointestinal tract. In mild cases, the disease can be asymptomatic for a long time. Complaints of bloody vomiting are detected in 85% of patients.

Keywords: Mallory-Weiss syndrome, oesophagus, oesophageal bleeding, tears, angiotherapy, endoscopy.

One of the most important risk factors for Mallory-Weiss syndrome is excessive alcohol consumption, as more than 50% of patients with this diagnosis have abused alcohol.[1] The severity of bleeding from the upper gastrointestinal tract in Mallory-Weiss syndrome is increased by the simultaneous presence of portal hypertension and esophageal varices.

There is also some suspicion of a relationship between hiatal hernia and Mallory-Weiss syndrome, but this is still under discussion. In most cases of Mallory-Weiss syndrome, a hiatal hernia is detected, but a study conducted at the Mayo Clinic in Florida found no difference in the incidence of hiatal hernia between patients with Mallory-Weiss syndrome and controls.[3]

Other risk factors for this syndrome include bulimia nervosa, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), and gravitational esophageal edema. In all these conditions, there is regurgitation of gastric contents into the esophagus. In 1/4 of cases, patients did not have any of the above risk factors. Many underlying disorders that cause vomiting and belching, as well as coughing, cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) or blunt abdominal trauma lead to an increase in intra-abdominal pressure and can provoke the disease. This syndrome can also occur as a complication of invasive procedures such as upper gastrointestinal endoscopy (0.07% to 0.49%) or transesophageal echocardiography.

According to available data, the age of highest incidence is between 40 and 60 years. Men are 2-4 times more likely to have Mallory-Weiss syndrome than women for unclear reasons. In the United States, Mallory-Weiss syndrome accounts for 1% to 15% of the causes of upper gastrointestinal bleeding in adults and less than 5% in children.

The exact mechanism of Mallory-Weiss syndrome is not known for certain. The most likely theory is that when intra-abdominal pressure suddenly and severely increases, gastric contents are thrown into the esophagus under pressure. This overpressure of gastric contents leads to longitudinal tears in the mucous membrane, which can reach the submucosal arteries and

veins, and this leads to bleeding in the upper gastrointestinal tract.[2]

This disease can be asymptomatic in mild cases. The most important and main symptom is vomiting of blood in 85% of cases. Vomiting can range from bloody mucus to intense red bleeding, depending on the amount of blood. Other symptoms may also occur, such as stools with blood impurities, dizziness or syncope, in the presence of massive bleeding. In most cases, there is pain in the epigastric region, which indicates a predisposing factor for the development of bleeding, such as the gastroesophageal reflex. There are no specific physical signs for Mallory-Weiss syndrome, and the signs are similar to other hemorrhagic conditions or shock. During the objective examination, it is necessary to check for signs of massive bleeding and shock, but not limited to this, but also to check for tachycardia, thready pulse, hypotension, dehydration, decreased skin turgor and capillary refill time and provide immediate treatment if present. Signs of melena can be detected by rectal examination. After an objective examination, patients should be sorted according to the severity of bleeding.

When a patient is admitted with bloody vomiting, it is necessary to provide emergency medical care. First of all, we take the patient's history and complaints. After that, we need to conduct an objective examination of the patient and understand the severity of the bleeding. Some patients may have significant internal bleeding, and a thorough history and objective examination are vital. Laboratory tests include: complete blood count, coagulogram. In Mallory-Weiss syndrome, a complete blood count will show a decreased platelet count, decreased hemoglobin, and a decreased red blood cell count. The coagulogram will have an increased prothrombin time. It is also necessary to do tests that examine kidney function in order to check for renal failure (determination of creatinine and blood urea nitrogen). An ECG is performed to exclude myocardial infarction or ischemia. The leading diagnostic method is esophagogastroduodenoscopy, with special attention to the upper gastrointestinal tract. During the

endoscopy, "Mallory-Weiss tears", linear tears of the mucous membrane, and blood clots will be observed on the esophageal mucosa. Linear tears in the proximal part of the small curvature of the stomach, just below the cardia, confirm the diagnosis.

Studies with barium should be avoided due to low diagnostic value and obstacles to endoscopic examination.

Mallory-Weiss syndrome usually does not require treatment and recovery occurs when the etiologic factor is eliminated. That is why the primary treatment is aimed at stabilizing the patient's general condition.

In case of active bleeding, the patient should receive emergency medical care immediately upon admission to the hospital. First of all, we assess hemodynamics, check the airway, breathing and blood circulation. It is necessary to start intravenous rehydration measures. Infusion of packed red blood cells is indicated if the hemoglobin level is below 80 g/l or if the patient has signs of shock or heavy bleeding.

Coagulation factors should be optimized before proceeding to endoscopic examination.

For medical treatment, PPIs (proton pump inhibitors) are used - omeprazole, pantoprazole, as well as H2-histamine receptor blockers - famotidine to reduce gastric acidity. Antiemetics such as metaclopramide are prescribed to control nausea and vomiting.

Endoscopic treatment is used if there is prolonged active or recurrent bleeding. A local injection of epinephrine is performed to stop the bleeding due to vasoconstriction. There is also a method of stopping active bleeding called multipolar electrocoagulation. There are also injections of sclerosant.[4][5]

Angiotherapy is used when endoscopy is unavailable or ineffective. Vasopressin is used in injection for vasoconstriction, or transcatheter embolization with gel foam is used for obliteration of the mesenteric arteries.

Surgical treatment it is required in rare cases and is considered necessary after ineffective endoscopic treatment. Linear tears are sutured laparoscopically under the control of endoscopy. In very severe cases, compression with a Sengstaken-Blakemore tube is used.

Differential diagnosis is performed with other causes of bleeding from the upper gastrointestinal tract:

1. Burhave syndrome: the clinical picture is similar, but the pathology is perforation of the esophagus.
2. Peptic ulcer of the upper gastrointestinal tract.
3. Tumors of the esophagus and the pro-acidic section of the stomach.
4. Esophageal varices: occurs as a complication of portal hypertension.

Conclusion.

So, above we have considered that Mallory-Weiss syndrome is linear tears of the mucous membrane of the cardioesophageal zone, which occur against the background of vomiting, hiccups. The number of patients with this diagnosis is increasing every year. The treatment of Mallory-Weiss syndrome is quite complicated. However, due to the emergence of new treatment methods, such as endoscopy and angiotherapy, it is now possible to fully recover and live a full life.

References

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